

1,2,3,4,5-Pentaarylpentane-1, 5-diones.

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A number of 1,2,3,4,5-pentaarylpentane-1,5-diones are described. They have been synthesized in a single step condensation of desoxybenzoin and aryl aldehydes.

In a synthetic procedure towards pentaphenylcyclopentanes, a number of 1,2,3,4,5-pentaarylpentane-1,5-diones (III, amarones) were prepared. A few such systems have been made earlier in two separate steps¹⁻⁴, these being an acid catalysed aldol condensation of desoxybenzoin (I) and aryl aldehydes (II), followed by a base catalysed Michael addition of a second molecule of desoxybenzoin to the condensation products (arylidenedesoxybenzoins). A small quantity of benzamarone has been found as a product in aldol condensation of desoxybenzoin with benzaldehyde with aqueous potassium hydroxide as catalyst¹.

It is found that good yields of 1,2,3,4,5-pentaarylpentane-1,5-diones (III) are obtained in the condensation of desoxybenzoin with aryl aldehydes in ethanolic sodium ethoxide. However, these amarones were not found to be in the potassium tertiary butoxide catalysed reaction.

The compounds show a single typical intense ultraviolet absorption at 235 to 250 m μ (log ϵ = 4.1 to 4.5) corresponding to benzoyl groups which apparently mask all the other less intense phenyl absorption bands. The products are insoluble in most solvents and are crystallized from hot acetic acid or 2-methoxyethanol.

Several attempts at reduction of the keto group failed and the 1,2,3,4,5-pentaarylpentane-1,5-diones were recovered in quantitative yields.

EXPERIMENTAL

1,2,4,5-Tetraphenyl-3-(3',4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-pentane-1,5-dione (III Ar = 3,4-dimethoxyphenyl): A mixture of desoxybenzoin (3.9 g) and veratraldehyde (3.3 g) was added to a well stirred solution of ethanolic sodium ethoxide prepared by dissolving sodium (0.9 g) in absolute alcohol (20 ml.). After stirring for 20 min. at room temperature the reaction mixture was acidified with 6*N*-hydrochloric acid (8 ml.), and then most of the alcohol was distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue on filtration and washing with ether

TABLE
Preparation of 1,2,3,4,5-pentaarylpentane-1,5-diones

Aldehyde used	m.p.		Yield (%)	Analysis %			Calcd.	EtOH λ_{max} $m\mu$	log ϵ
	Found	Lit.		Found	Found	Found			
1. Benzaldehyde	219°	219° ¹	100	—	—	—	—	250	4.12
2. <i>p</i> -Tolualdehyde	241-242°	233-234° ³	48	—	—	—	—	—	—
3. Anisaldehyde	242°	—	96	84.79	5.70	—	84.70	235	4.10
4. <i>m</i> -methoxybenzaldehyde	214-216°	—	62	85.08	5.72	—	84.70	256*	—
5. 3:4-Dimethoxybenzaldehyde	190°	—	95	82.46	5.85	—	82.22	240	4.52
6. 3:4-methylenedioxybenzaldehyde	247°	243-244° ³	51	—	—	—	—	244.5	4.42
7. <i>m</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	222°	220° ¹	27	—	—	—	—	250	4.45
8. <i>o</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	196°	—	62	81.40	5.16	6.62	81.52	247*	—
9. <i>p</i> -Chlorobenzaldehyde	234°	—	60	81.59	5.49	6.71	81.52	248	4.45
10. Furfural	194°	—	24	84.38	5.80	—	84.26	245	4.74

* Practically insoluble in ethanol, hence spectra of a saturated solution was taken.

gave 1,2,4,5-tetraphenyl-3-(3', 4'-dimethoxyphenyl)-pentane-1,5-dione (5.2 g.), m.p. 190°, on crystallisation from hot acetic acid. (Found : C, 82.46, H, 5.85. Calcd. for $C_{37}H_{32}O_4$: C, 82.22; H, 5.92%). λ_{max}^{EtOH} 240 m μ (log ϵ 4.52).

Other diones were prepared similarly (see table).

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